

Coon and Tucker *“Measuring motivation for alfalfa hay in feedlot cattle using an aversive stimulus as a tradeoff”*

Instructions for daily electrified barrier assessment

Daily Gate Inspection

As you inspect each component of the gate, please write either a “1” if that component is in good condition, a “0” if it needs repair on the “Daily Gate Inspection” sheet or “NA” if it doesn’t apply to that gate type. Gate types include: **E** – Electrified, **W** – Wooden trainer, **MW** – Magnetized wooden trainer, and **A** – Acrylic trainer. The current levels include: NA (for all gate types except E), 0, 156, 312, 625, 1250, 2500, and 5000.

1. Write your name, the date, and circle either “AM” or “PM” at the top of the “Daily Gate Inspection” sheet.
2. Determine if the “Gate Type” specified is correct for each bin number.
3. Assess if gate is hanging level and that the magnets are securely attached.
 - a. If the gate is not level, use the socket wrench to adjust the u-clips. The gate is level if the magnets connect easily.
 - b. If a magnet has fallen off or is damaged, replace the magnet with a fresh one. A magnet must first be folded into a piece of duct tape and then folded again into a strip of white drawer liner. That magnet can then be secured to the gate or bin using the staple gun.

Example of a level gate:

Example of an unlevel gate:

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Example of securely attached magnets:

Example of unsecured magnets:

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Example of a damaged magnet. The magnet has become unattached to the bin and is freely attached to the opposite magnet on the gate:

4. Check for food, debris, or saliva that may be caught in the chicken wire.
 - a. If you need to touch the chicken wire for any reason, unclasp the alligator clips so that you will not be shocked. Please reattach the alligator clips, one on each piece of chicken wire, before continuing.
 - b. If needed, wipe the food or debris off of the chicken wire using a brush. Saliva can be removed using a piece of paper towel.

Example of clean chicken wire, free of debris:

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Example of debris caught in the chicken wire:

5. Unclip alligator clips to avoid being shocked and then scrub chicken wire with green sponge to ensure metal is exposed and not coated with anything. Reattach alligator clips before proceeding to next step.

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6. Make sure there is no loose chicken wire or staples.
 - a. If wire has come loose, use the staple gun to properly secure the chicken wire in place.
 - b. If a staple has come loose, remove it using pliers and replace it with a fresh staple.

Example of loose chicken wire:

7. Ensure that the two heat lamps are positioned correctly and turned on.

Example of lamps correctly positioned:

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8. Assess if the gate is shocking properly:
 1. Trigger the motion sensor to power the shocker by walking within 10 feet in front of the sensor. The shocker will turn off if the motion sensor is not triggered again within 30 minutes.
 2. Toggle upwards on the “Menu” button to select present 9. For example, if the shocker reads “Ready 0: 0156 μ A”, toggle upwards on the “Menu” button (highlighted in the yellow box) until it reads “Ready 9: 0400 μ A”.

3. Position the shocker so that the manual trigger is pushed down by the bolt and the screen reads “Shocking 0400 μ A”.
4. Compare the shock intensity between the hanging gate and a fresh gate from the office by switching the alligator clips between the two gates. Be sure to attach alligator clips to two separate (not touching or joined in any way) pieces of chicken wire.
 - a. If they feel the same, the gate is shocking correctly.
 - b. If the shock intensity is not as strong as the fresh gate, it will need to be replaced.

Example of alligator clips attached correctly to two separate but adjacent pieces of chicken wire:

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Example of alligator clips attached **incorrectly** to the same piece of chicken wire:

Note: If the gate is not shocking at all, make sure the “Shock” button is properly triggered (a yellow light will turn on above the word “SHOCK”). Next, make sure the screen reads “SHOCKING” and not “Ready”. Finally, check that the red light under “2” is lit up and not the red light under “8” on the right-hand side of the shocker (highlighted in the yellow box).

9. Set the shocker to the correct preset using the assigned current.
10. Have another person confirm that preset is correctly set up on shocker.
11. Determine if the “Current” specified is correct for relevant gates (only E gates, otherwise write “NA”).

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Daily Gate Inspection Datasheet

Enter “1” if component is in working order as described under the “Component” section of table. Enter “0” if component is not as described or is broken. Enter “NA” if component does not apply to bin. Gate types include: E – Electrified, W – Wooden trainer, MW – Magnetized wooden trainer, and A – Acrylic trainer. The current levels include: NA (for all gate types except E), 0, 156, 312, 625, 1250, 2500, and 5000.

Component	Bin #	Bin #	Bin #	Bin #	Bin #	Bin #	Bin #	Bin #	Bin #
Gate Type:	Current:								
Correct Gate Type and Current									
Gate is hanging level and magnets are firmly attached.									
Chicken wire is free of feed, debris, and saliva.									
Did you scrub the gate with the green sponge?									
There are no loose wires or staples.									
Two heat lamps are correctly positioned and turned on.									
Gate is shocking.									
Alligator clips are correctly attached.									
Notes:									